

SpaceTeamSat1
Critical Design Document
System Architecture

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Version 1.2

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Review History

The Critical Design Review (CDR) consists of two parts: First, this document itself, and second, a review meeting in which the topics are discussed in person. In the following table, the invited reviewers are listed. Additionally, it is stated if feedback to the document was received (DOC) as well as if the person participated in the CDR meeting (CDR).

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Contribution	Re-viewer	Email	Justification
Some words are misleading, Powerlines shall not act as an electric motor, does the Antenna deployment still works at very low temperatures	Lars Mehnen	lars.mehnen@techniku-wien.at	SSETI Express/RF specialist
Nomenclature check, Project planning	Philip Olbrich	philip@olbrich.tech	Beyond Gravity - Software Product Owner

Authors

Contribution	Name	Email
TU Wien Space Team	-	office@spaceteam.at
Project lead, System Architecture	David Wagner	david.wagner@spaceteam.at
System Architecture, COBC	Jakob Riepler	jakob.riepler@spaceteam.at
System Architecture	Patrick Kappl	patrick.kappl@spaceteam.at
System Architecture	Daniel Schloms	daniel.schloms@spaceteam.at
EPS	David Freismuth	david.freismuth@spaceteam.at

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List of Acronyms

1U	One-Unit CubeSat ($10 \times 10 \times 10 \text{ cm}^3$ and max. 1.33 kg)	FRAM	Ferroelectric Random Access Memory
ACK	Acknowledgment (signal)	FRR	Flight Readiness Review
ADCS	Attitude Determination and Control System	FX.25	Protocol extension to AX.25
AHS	Allgemeinbildende Höhere Schule	FYS	Fly Your Satellite! programme of ESA [3]
ANT	Antenna System	GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
AX.25	A data link layer protocol	GS	Ground Station
BHS	Berufsbildende Höhere Schule	HAF	High-altitude flight
CAM	Camera module	ISS	International Space Station
CCSDS	A file transfer protocol	LEO	Low Earth Orbit
CDR	Critical Design Review	MCU	Microcontroller Unit
COM	Communication module	MOSFET	Metal Oxide Semiconductor Field Effect Transistor
COTS	Commercial Off-The-Shelf	MPPT	Maximum Power Point Tracking
COBC	Communication Module and On-board Computer	OBC	On-Board Computer
CSI	Camera Serial Interface	PCB	Printed Circuit Board
DS	Deployment Switch	PD	Preliminary Design
DT	Deployment Timer	PDR	Preliminary Design Review
EDU	Education module	SC	Solar Cells
eMMC	Embedded MultiMediaCard	RBF	Remove Before Flight pin
EPS	Electrical Power System	RF	Radio Frequency
ESA	European Space Agency	RTC	Real-Time Clock
ESERO	European Space Education Resource Office[1]	SatNOGS	Satellite Networked Open Ground Station
FEC	Forward Error Correction	SRAM	Static Random Access Memory
FFG	Österreichische Forschungsförderungsgesellschaft (Austrian Research Promotion Agency) [2]	STS1	SpaceTeamSat1 – name of CubeSat mission and CubeSat platform
		SW	Software
		UCI	Umbilical Cord Interface

1. Introduction

This document serves as the system architecture Critical Design (CD) for the CubeSat mission SpaceTeamSat1 (STS1), which is designed by the TU Wien Space Team [4]. It describes the system architecture and presents the basic concepts of the key components of the CubeSat mission. From a functional point of view, the Electrical Power System (EPS)[5] and the Communication Module and On-board Computer (COBC)[6, 7] are the most important components of the CubeSat. Therefore, the main focus lies on these components as well as on the dataflow of the complete CubeSat mission – including the Ground Station (GS) infrastructure. More details regarding the dataflow were developed within the Dataflow Game, which is separately documented [8].

The document is organized as listed in the following: In Section 1.1 and Section 1.2, the mission statement and the main objectives, on which the CubeSat mission is based on, are presented. In Chapter 2, the top high-level requirements and most relevant system requirements of the mission are stated and described in more detail. These requirements are based on the mission objectives, and build the base for the mission concept and the design of the CubeSat. In Chapter 3, an overview of the CubeSat system architecture and its subsystems is given. First, the dataflow from the Earth-based infrastructure to the CubeSat is evaluated for up- and down-link. This information is then used to derive the basic concepts of the subsystems. Note that a profound analysis of the dataflow was extracted by executing the Dataflow Game, which is documented in Ref. [8].

1. Introduction

Main properties of the CubeSat mission SpaceTeamSat1

- Mission and CubeSat name: SpaceTeamSat1 (short: STS1)
- 1U ($10 \times 10 \times 12 \text{ cm}^3$ approximately 1.2 kg) CubeSat platform
- STS1 shall operate in Low Earth Orbit (LEO) (350 km–500 km)
- STS1 shall be a lab for students of AHS and BHS
- STS1 shall enable access to the amateur radio community for students
- Educational mission objective:
 - Student teams compete in a space-related coding competition.
 - Python code which runs on the educational payload of the CubeSat (Raspberry Pi) platform.
 - Many possible software scenarios are possible. Therefore, various sensors are available for read-out.
 - Gathered data is handed over to participating students for further evaluation of the received data.
 - Student teams shall present their acquired results and therefore gain important insights into space-related technologies.
- The education module (EDU) with its sensors is the educational payload of the CubeSat:
 - Temperature sensor
 - Magnetometers
 - Accelerometers
 - Gyroscopes
 - Dosimeter
 - Brightness sensors
 - Cameras

1.1. Mission Statement

Excitement and enthusiasm for engineering and science are important features of a progressive society. They are a consequence of the urge to explore the universe, which is deeply rooted in human nature. Nowadays, space technologies enable humankind to satisfy this urge and reach out further than ever before. However, even though space technologies are deeply ingrained within pop culture and organizations like NASA, ESA, or SpaceX successfully conduct widely publicized missions, a hands-on approach to these topics seems out of reach for most people. Therefore, we want to provide an entry point into space technologies for students of secondary schools by giving them the opportunity to run their own software experiments on our self-developed CubeSat platform, which is “Made in Austria”. We hope that this will broaden their educational horizon and thus inspire the next generation of space and science enthusiasts.

1.2. Mission Objectives

The mission objectives build the base for any space-related project as they give reasons why certain tasks need to be executed in space, which are mostly complex and costly. They state the relevance of the mission as well as its importance and allow the derivation of requirements and, later on, the design and operation of the CubeSat. The mission objectives for STS1 are separated into primary and secondary mission objectives, which indicate the relevance of the individual objectives.

Primary objectives:

1. To develop and build a working satellite
2. To operate our self-developed CubeSat
3. To give students a platform to run their self-developed software on a CubeSat
4. To inspire students to be part of a space project

Secondary objectives:

5. To take an image from space
6. To make the gathered data and insights available to the public and especially other CubeSat missions

2. System Requirements

The mission objectives build the base of any CubeSat mission, as described in Chapter 1, and are therefore used for the definition of the system requirements. The presented system requirements in this CD are high-level requirements with the goal of determining the necessary subsystems which build the base of the CubeSat platform. All requirements shall be measurable and verifiable. Furthermore, requirements shall answer the “Why?” by specifying the “What?” and not addressing the “How?”. For nomenclature reasons, we use the same wording to formulate requirements as in the Fly Your Satellite! (FYS) design specification [3] by ESA:

- The word “shall” is used to express requirements that have to be met.
- The word “should” is used to express recommendations.
- The word “may” is used to express permissions.

Furthermore, we use the following to specify where a requirement is fulfilled:

- The quote “Fulfilled by” is used to express that a requirement is fulfilled by other sub requirements.
- The quote “Fulfilled in” is used to express that a requirement is fulfilled in a section within the same document.

The following mission requirements are derived from the mission objectives:

- 1 The CubeSat shall have a system to generate power and distribute it to all other subsystems.

Note: It shall be possible that the CubeSat can be powered solely by the solar cells, solely by the batteries, respectively both. The power distribution is only active in the operation phase of the CubeSat mission.

Fulfilled: By 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.4

- 2 The CubeSat shall automatically charge the batteries as long as there is excess energy available.

Note: Excess energy is the difference between the power provided by the solar cells and the power needed to power the subsystems of the CubeSat.

Fulfilled: By 2.1

- 3 The CubeSat shall automatically transmit a beacon at least once every 30 seconds.

Note: Obviously, this can only be done if enough power is provided.

Fulfilled: By 3.1

- 4 The CubeSat shall be able to receive commands, when not transmitting data.

Note: The CubeSat shall portion large amounts of data before transmission. After a certain amount of transmitted data the CubeSat has a transmission dead-time, which can be used to receive commands.

Fulfilled: By 4.1

2. System Requirements

5 The CubeSat shall have a compact and interchangeable electronic stack.

Note: This should allow for easy interchangeability of different subsystems or a different payload in a possible future scenario.

Fulfilled: By [5.1](#), [5.2](#), [5.3](#), [5.4](#)

6 The CubeSat shall have a single master, which is the COBC.

Note: The master is the only subsystem that is able to initiate active communication with other subsystems on the CubeSat platform.

Fulfilled: By [6.1](#), [6.2](#)

7 The primary ground station shall be able to send data and commands to the CubeSat. The primary ground station shall also be able to receive data from the CubeSat.

Note: The communication capabilities shall be verified by a HAF, where the CubeSat shall be placed in a weather balloon. Additional GSs should be able to receive data from the CubeSat.

Fulfilled: By [7.1](#), [7.2](#), [7.3](#), [7.4](#), [7.5](#), [7.6](#)

8 The EDU module shall be operable for at least 10% of the mission duration. The maximum continuous uptime of the EDU shall be at least 3 h.

Fulfilled: By [8.1](#)

9 The CubeSat shall be able to execute Python code, written by high school students.

Fulfilled: By [9.1](#), [9.2](#), [9.3](#), [9.4](#), [9.5](#), [9.6](#), [9.7](#), [9.8](#)

10 STS1 shall comply with the CubeSat Design Specification Rev 13 [[9](#)], requirement 3.1 to 3.4.

Note: The launch provider requires us to fulfill these requirements for the deployer.

Verified: By Inspection.

11 STS1 shall comply with the Requirements from the 2nd Launch User Guideline from ISAR Aerospace [[9](#)] chapter 5.

Note: The launch provider requires each customer to fulfill these requirements.

Verified: By the test campaign which will be done on the flight model.

2. System Requirements

The following system requirements are deduced from mission requirement 1:

- 1.1 STS1 shall power all systems, via the CSBI, if enough energy comes from the SCs and once it reached the operational phase.

Fulfilled: By 1-EPS-11 [5]

- 1.2 STS1 shall have a mechanism in place to power all systems, via the CSBI, if there is enough energy in the batteries and once it reaches the operational phase.

Fulfilled: By 1-EPS-11 [5]

- 1.3 Each Subsystem of STS1 shall be powered, via the CSBI, by a voltage level between 5 V and 8.4 V.

Note: This means that each subsystem is responsible for generating its own voltage levels, e.g. constant 5 V or 3.3 V.

Fulfilled: By 1.3.COBC.1 [6], 1-EPS-9 [5], 1.3.EDU.1 [10]

- 1.4 The power generating subsystem of STS1 shall provide a voltage level with a ripple lower than 100 mV.

Note: This means that each subsystem is responsible for generating its own voltage levels, e.g. constant 5 V or 3.3 V

Fulfilled: By 1.4.COBC.1 [6], 1-EPS-10 [5], 1.4.EDU.1 [10]

The following system requirements are deduced from mission requirement 2:

- 2.1 The CubeSat shall automatically recharge the batteries when there is spare energy.

Fulfilled: By design, described in chapter 2.1.1. [5]

The following system requirements are deduced from mission requirement 3:

- 3.1 The CubeSat shall automatically send out a beacon at least once every 30 seconds, with a tolerance of ± 5 s.

Note: Only if it has power.

Fulfilled: By 3.1.COBC.1 [6], 3.1.COBC_SW.1 [7]

The following system requirements are deduced from mission requirement 4:

- 4.1 The CubeSat shall always be able to receive a command in an acceptable amount of send time.

Note: This means that the continuous sending is not allowed to take longer than about ten seconds. After this sending, the CubeSat must switch to a receive state where it waits for at least one second to receive a command.

Fulfilled: By 4.1.COBC_SW.1 [7]

The following system requirements are deduced from mission requirement 5:

- 5.1 The CubeSat shall have two bus connectors, which ensure communication between all the subsystems.

Note: Those bus connectors shall be located on opposite sides of the PCBs. This should allow for easier electric wiring on the PCBs.

Note: Not all Subsystem need to be connected to both bus connectors, respectively the top and bottom PCBs.

2. System Requirements

Fulfilled: By 5.1.COBC.1 [6], 1-EPS-8 [5], 5.1.EDU.1 [10]

5.2 The CubeSat shall have a reusable satellite framework.

Note: This means that the hardware of the subsystems COM, EPS, and OBC shall work independently of the science payload (here: EDU module). However, software dependency is not prohibited.

Fulfilled: By 5.2.COBC.1 to 5.2.COBC.3 [6], 1-EPS-5 [5]

5.3 No subsystem that needs the CSBI X+ shall be located above the science payload PCB(s) (here: EDU module) in the electronic stack.

Note: Sensor PCBs are not subsystems.

Fulfilled: In 3.1

Verified: By system design.

5.4 The CubeSat shall have an antenna release mechanism. The mechanism shall be controlled via the master and powered via the EPS.

Fulfilled: By 5.5.COBC.1 [6], 1-EPS-15 [5]

The following system requirements are deduced from mission requirement 6:

6.1 The CubeSat shall be able to deactivate all systems not necessary for communication once a command is received to do so.

Note: All subsystems for communication are EPS and COBC. (TODO: Communication → GS to COM; Downstream/Upstream)

Fulfilled: In 3.1 and by 6.1.COBC_SW.1 to 6.1.COBC_SW.3[7], 6.1.EDU.1 [10]

Verified: By testing.

6.2 The CubeSat should have a central processing unit (here: COBC) which deactivates the EDU, if it is not used in the next couple of minutes.

Fulfilled: In 3.1 and by 6.2.COBC_SW.1 to 6.2.COBC_SW.2[7]

Verified: By recording the RF output of the CubeSat during sending of a big data package which takes 60 seconds to send.

The following system requirements are deduced from mission requirement 7:

7.1 The CubeSat shall be able to receive one full program code at least once every 24 hours.

Note: One full program code stands for the maximum possible code size that can be flashed on the EDU μ C, which is 1 MiB.

Fulfilled: By 7.1.COBC_SW.1 [7]

7.2 The GS shall be able to send commands and data to the CubeSat.

Fulfilled: By 7.2.GS.1 [11] to 7.2.GS.3 [11]

7.3 The GS shall be able to download data from the CubeSat and store it locally within the GS infrastructure.

Fulfilled: By 7.3.GS.1 [11] to 7.3.GS.3 [11]

7.4 The GS shall be able to run for at least seven days.

Fulfilled: By 7.4.GS.1 [11]

2. System Requirements

- 7.5 STS1 shall be able to download the entire generated data of one student code at least once every 48 hours.

Note: The entire generated data is equivalent to the maximum data one student code generates during its whole run time, this is equivalent to the memory size in which the student code stores its data. This restricts the maximum amount of data and the number of photos a student code can produce, which is 1 MiB.

Fulfilled: By 7.5.COBC.1 [6], 7.5.COBC_SW.1 [7], 7.5.GS.1 [11] and 7.5.GS.2 [11]

- 7.6 All operations of the GS shall be configured to run manually or Autonomously.

Note: “Autonomously” means that it does not require any human action.

Fulfilled: By 7.6.GS.1 [11]

The following system requirements are deduced from mission requirement 8:

- 8.1 The CubeSat shall have a higher average power input, measured over one full orbiting cycle, than the maximum average power drain from all the subsystems, also measured over one full orbiting cycle.

Note: For the rotation the worst expected rotation shall be used, after the detumbling phase. Maximum average refers to the maximum power drain a subsystem can have measured over one full orbiting cycle, e.g., the GS is below the CubeSat in the used cycle for the power drain calculation for the COM module. The detumbling phase ends when the change of rotation of the CubeSat falls below 1%, measured over one orbiting cycle.

Fulfilled: By design

Verified: By simulations that rotate the CubeSat with random axis with different speeds.

The following system requirements are deduced from mission requirement 9:

- 9.1 The CubeSat shall have several sensors integrated within the CubeSat.

Note: This should attract more attention and make the mission more interesting for the students to participate in.

Fulfilled: By 9.1.EDU.1 [10]

- 9.2 The CubeSat shall have multiple cameras which are suitable for an operation in space.

Note: This shall allow the CubeSat to take images of Earth in all possible orientations.

Fulfilled: By 9.2.EDU.1 [10]

- 9.3 The EDU should be able to recover from a small number of cosmic bit flips.

Fulfilled: By 9.3.EDU.1 [12]

- 9.4 The EDU shall be able to gracefully handle errors.

Fulfilled: By 9.4.EDU.1 to 9.4.EDU.2 [12]

Note: *Gracefully* in this context means, that the system is able to forward recover from a wide range of errors and stay operational. In the worst case it may turn itself off and leave recovery to the COBC.

2. System Requirements

9.5 The EDU shall be controlled by commands from the COBC.

Note: When supplied with power, the EDU shall boot into an operational state and then wait for commands sent by the COBC. Communication follows a strict master–slave relationship between COBC and EDU.

Fulfilled: By 9.5.COBC_SW.1 to 9.5.COBC_SW.3 [7], 9.5.EDU.1 to 9.5.EDU.7 [10]

9.6 The EDU shall be able to deal with being turned off mid-operation.

Note: The EDU may be turned off any time if power gets low.

Fulfilled: By 9.6.EDU.1 [10]

9.7 The CubeSat team of the TU Wien Space Team shall be able to verify the student code, which was developed by the students on a Dev-Kit.

Note: This ensures that only fully functional code is executed on the CubeSat platform in Space. The Dev-Kit is a development environment, which contains the same sensors as mounted on the EDU module within the CubeSat. "Same sensors" does not mean the same physical implementation. On the Dev-Kit, also virtual sensors can be used (e.g. libraries of the individual sensors, which behave equally). The Dev-Kit allows the student teams to develop and test their code on Earth.

Fulfilled: In section 3.7

Verified: By testing of the students SW on the dev kit at the TU Wien Space Team.

9.8 The CubeSat shall be in orbit for at least six months which include January 1st and June 30th, not dependent on the year and not dependent on the launch date.

Note: This range is chosen as it includes the second half of a school year in Austria. This allows us to gradually build up the knowledge of the students over the first half of a school year and run the student codes in the second half of the school year.

Verified: The program DRAMA and the expected orbital parameters.

3. System Architecture

The following chapter discusses the basic concepts of the individual subsystems of STS1, namely the Electrical Power System (EPS)[5], the Communication Module and On-board Computer (COBC)[6, 7] and the Education module (EDU)[10]. As the received and transmitted data build the base of the whole CubeSat platform, Section 3.3 describes the dataflow from the ground infrastructure to the CubeSat in more detail. In a next step the EPS – power generation and distribution – is investigated. Therefore, Section 3.4 discusses the conceptual design of the EPS. In a next step the COBC is presented in Section 3.5. The COBC is the main processing and scheduling unit of the CubeSat and also handles the RF communication. Finally, Section 3.6 describes the concept of the EDU. This subsystem is the educational payload of the CubeSat mission and therefore executes the software experiments that are provided by the individual student teams, i.e., participating schools. The EDU is equipped with multiple sensors, including two cameras (CAM), to perform various experiments.

Figure 3.1.: Basic system architecture of STS1. The arrows determine the direction of data- (black), power- (blue) and inhibit-flow (red).

Figure 3.1 shows the basic system architecture of the CubeSat and the associated ground infrastructure. The Antenna System (ANT) is used to communicate with the COBC, which contains the RF module for receiving and transmitting data. The Solar Cells (SC) are directly connected to the EPS and are used to harvest electrical energy. The main Ground Station (GS) can be accessed from any PC on Earth via the Internet. The Umbilical Cord Interface (UCI) allows us to re-program the COBC and charge batteries, which are operated by the EPS, after assembling the CubeSat. The Deployment Switches (DS) and the Remove-Before-Flight pin (RBF) ensure that the CubeSat is not powered in the safely stored configuration (e.g. in the chassis of the carrier rocket). Within the EDU module, the Camera module (CAM) can receive image acquisition commands.

3.1. STS1 System Layout

There is only one electronic stack in the CubeSat, which contains all the subsystem PCBs, excluding the SidePCBs. Starting in the positive direction of the X-axis, from bottom to top, the stack is ordered as follows: COBC, EPS, EDU, Dosimeter, this can be seen in [3.2](#)

Figure 3.2.: STS1 exploded view

3.3. Dataflow

This section discusses the flow of data and commands from the ground infrastructure to the CubeSat and its internal subsystems.

The GS can be separated into three main parts.

TX

The first part is our physical primary GS , which will have a LHCP antenna on a mount that is able to rotate in both azimuth and elevation axis to actively track the CubeSat. It will be controlled by a Raspberry Pi running the SatNogs software stack which we will extend with transmit capabilities.

RX

The second part is the SatNogs database and network, which will be used for scheduling observations, for publicly recording all received data, and for publishing a public dashboard featuring decoded telemetry data . Additionally, we will extend our downlink capacity by utilizing other receive-only GS connected to the SatNogs network to receive beacons sent by the STS1, and possibly, also all other telemetry packages.

GS-SW

The last part is our software stack (based on COSMOS [13]) that is responsible for providing us with an interface to encode and schedule commands for the CubeSat and decode any received data from the CubeSat. It also includes a database, which stores relevant data from all packages sent or received.

The following subsections discuss the basic deliberations of the dataflow processes.

3.3.1. Protocol

As the RF communication should attract the amateur radio community, AX.25 (FX.25) or CCSDS protocols are considered to be used for communicating with the CubeSat. Both protocols provide similar functionality and have different strengths. As both protocols do not provide an application layer protocol, custom software will be necessary for packet decoding anyways, which dampens the “well known protocol”-argument by a bit. Currently, we are still evaluating which of those two options (or a mix of them) is best suited for the STS1 mission. The final decision will be made as soon as the hardware and software topology of the COBC is defined in a more confident matter.

AX.25

The amateur radio “standard” AX.25 based protocol stack mainly provides a well-known protocol and will probably aid with adoption in the amateur radio community. However, it was not built with space links in mind, which requires special considerations to support this highly asymmetric link topology.

CCSDS

The CCSDS protocol stack on the other hand was built specifically with space links and their quirks in mind, providing convolutional channel coding and Forward Error Correction (FEC) for improved error immunity.

Interoperability, Security Measures

To prevent others from hijacking (taking control of) STS1, only packages signed by the TU Wien Space Team are accepted by the CubeSat. This means that other interested amateur radio operators could establish an uplink as well, if the signature is shared. To increase the downlink capabilities, it is considered to cooperate with SatNOGS [14]. If so, the SatNOGS stations would increase the reception area of STS1. An additional self-built SatNOGS station would furthermore allow to create an additional educational platform for students and the TU Wien Space Team. The downlink is neither signed nor encrypted¹, enabling everyone in the amateur radio community to receive beacons and other data from STS1. This helps to increase the area of reception, which is especially useful when downloading big amounts of data. However, it needs to be considered that a proper management of the acquired data needs to be implemented.

Figure 3.4.: High-level dataflow diagram of STS1. Additionally, the relevant datatypes are mentioned for each data-link between subsystems.

3.3.2. Beacons

The CubeSat shall periodically broadcast housekeeping data (beacons) at least once a minute. However, it is targeted to increase the number of beacons per minute significantly. For this, the Microcontroller Unit (MCU) on the COBC gathers housekeeping data from sensors which are located on the EPS and on the COBC. The data is subsequently stored on the external COBC memory. Before a transmission to the GS, the COBC prepares the beacon for a broadcast by the RF module. Additionally, the beacon data will be stored in the external COBC memory over long periods of time, so that a history of beacon data can be requested by an appropriate command from the GS. Thus, history data can be obtained and evaluated easily.

These beacons can be received by any GS in range of the CubeSat at the broadcasting time. They include telemetry, housekeeping and operation status data.

3.3.3. Uplink

The GS can send signed commands and data via an RF uplink to the RF module of the COBC. The MCU on the COBC interprets these commands and data, and reacts accordingly. Commands will

¹Encryption is neither necessary, nor permitted by amateur radio regulations.

3. System Architecture

always rely on some sort of acknowledgment. Note that, e.g. CCSDS already has an ACK mechanism implemented.

In the following, the different data types which can be transmitted by the GS to the CubeSat are listed:

COBC firmware update

If a COBC firmware update is transmitted to the CubeSat, the MCU stores it in the external memory of the COBC. Afterwards, a command to the CubeSat is able to trigger a reset of the MCU and causes it to flash the new firmware stored in the external memory. A detailed concept for managing the firmware versions on the COBC needs to be considered during the COBC development. An initial approach is described in Section 3.5.

EDU programs

If the uploaded data is a program for the EDU module (Raspberry Pi), the uploaded data is stored in the external COBC memory. Note that an additional memory block dedicated for unique program IDs is available as well. The program IDs enable us to implement a queuing mechanism, which lists the program IDs which are executed sequentially. To schedule the execution of a new EDU program, first, the EDU program file has to be transmitted to the CubeSat. Afterwards, the EDU execution queue – consisting of program IDs and additional (not yet defined) parameters (i.e. relative timing) – is transmitted to the CubeSat. As soon as a matching EDU program and program ID are available – and enough power can be provided by the EPS to run the EDU – the COBC initiates the execution of the EDU program. The program ID list is executed sequentially till there are no more operation commands available.

EDU execution queue

If the uploaded data is an execution queue for the EDU programs, this data is stored on the external memory of the COBC. As described in the previous paragraph, this execution queue contains the information in which order to execute the EDU programs. The only possibility to modify the EDU queue from the GS is to overwrite it. Additionally, commands will be implemented to delete this execution queue. More detailed information is given in Section 3.5.3.

3.3.4. Downlink

All data generated by the CubeSat is stored on the external memory managed by the COBC. As outlined in section 3.3.2, the MCU automatically downlinks beacon data periodically, which can be captured by the amateur radio community all over the globe. All other data, including data generated by the EDU module will merely be downlinked after an appropriate command is sent to the CubeSat. As no dedicated details regarding the communication link is defined yet, no further processing steps from the GS to an individual PC can be given. However, this topic needs to be considered in the further development of the COBC and the satellite communication.

3.3.5. Execution of EDU programs

As mentioned previously, the execution of EDU programs depend on the EDU execution queue. For the execution of an EDU program, the program ID of the execution queue and the EDU program need to be compatible, i.e. the unique program ID can be “1a” and “1b”, for example, to be able to execute EDU program “1” two times. Additionally, the EPS needs to be able to provide enough power, which is signaled to the COBC by the EPS itself.

As soon as the program ID within the EDU execution queue and the EDU program are compatible and the power level provided by the EPS is within limits, the COBC starts the Raspberry Pi and transfers the correct EDU program to the Raspberry Pi for execution. No parallel executions will be possible. Therefore, the Raspberry Pi on the EDU module will merely execute one EDU program at a time. While the code is running, the Raspberry Pi has access to several sensors and two cameras to gather data. This data can be processed on the Raspberry Pi’s CPU. The (processed) data is temporarily stored on the Raspberry Pi’s internal memory. Note that basic limitations within the EDU execution queue need to be set to prevent infinite runs of EDU programs.

For permanent storage and transmission to ground, the data on the Raspberry Pi is transmitted to the external memory of the COBC. Within this operation, it needs to be ensured that the COBC still remains the master of the CubeSat platform. Therefore, the Raspberry Pi requests communication by setting a pin. The MCU decides when it has time to talk with the EDU, by doing so the EDU can tell the COBC that there is a new result available and send it to the COBC for it to store in its memory. The COBC updates its queues accordingly.

3.4. EPS – Electrical Power System

The Electrical Power System (EPS) is responsible for the continuous generation and provision of electrical power at a single, unregulated voltage level. Energy is harvested solely through solar cells. Excess energy is stored in batteries, in order to continue to power the satellite in orbit sections without light incidence. The EPS also contains system level safety features, like the Remove-Before-Flight pin (RBF), the Deployment Switches (DS) and a Deployment Timer (DT). All of these features shall prevent a premature activation, while the CubeSat is still mounted onto the launch vehicle. Housekeeping data like battery voltage, battery temperature, etc. is collected by the EPS, and made available to the COBC subsystem through a housekeeping data interface.

The following sections lay out the state of the art of commercial EPS' (Section 3.4.1), the architecture of the concept (Section 3.4.2) and the interfaces (Section 3.4.3) of the EPS.

3.4.1. State of the Art

As virtually any CubeSat hardware relies on electrical power, many commercial providers have gone through the effort of developing a ready-to-use Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) EPS. In Table 3.1 a comparison of a selection of providers and the estimated STS1 requirements are listed. It can be seen that commercial products are over-engineered in the majority of aspects. Especially when compared to the selection of available voltage rails and the capacity.

It has been decided to not implement a COTS EPS and rather develop the EPS in-house for the following reasons:

1. Building and sharing of know-how
2. Reduction of mission cost
3. Experiences from previous CubeSat missions suggest, that the EPS should be as simple as possible, should contain as few features as possible and should not contain any microcontrollers. This circumstance is not applicable to most available COTS EPS.

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	ISISpace[17]	Required for STS1		
Voltage Rails	BAT, 3.3 V, 5 V, configurable 3 V–18 V	BAT, 3.3 V, 5 V	BAT, 3.3 V, 5 V configurable	single voltage > 5 V
Capacity	11 W h	10 W h	22.5 W h	~ 2.33 W h
Power	20 W per rail	-	20 W per rail	~ 8.89 W
Mass	300 g	208 g	184 g	~ 300 g
Misc	RTC Software configurable	Serial Interfaces 6 General Purpose Outputs RBF and DS optional	Serial Interfaces FRAM based MCU Supervisor	No software DS Deployment Timer
Heaters	yes	yes	yes	no
Price	On Request	2.500€	3.300€	-

Table 3.1.: Comparison of the EPS' of a selection of providers and the estimated requirements of STS1. See Appendix A.1 for the source of the estimations.

3.4.2. Architecture

The system requirements 1 and 2, stated in Chapter 2, allow the deduction of the architecture depicted in Figure 3.6. The components and their functions are elaborated upon in the following list:

1. **External Charger:** Connects to the Umbilical Cord Interface (UCI) of the satellite and allows charging of the CubeSat batteries on the ground. It is possible to charge the batteries, even when the safety features of the CubeSat (i.e. DS, DT and RBF) are in effect. However, it is not possible to power other satellite subsystems via the external charger, while the safety features are in effect.
2. **Bus Gate:** Switch, that permanently connects the EPS-internal power bus to the system bus interface, once the deployment timer signal has been received.
3. **Battery Pack:** Contains battery cells that store excess energy generated by the solar cells. Allows operation of the satellite, when no energy is harvested by the solar cells.
4. **Temperature Sensor:** Measures the temperature of the battery pack, and distributes this information to the housekeeping block and to the battery controller.
5. **Solar Cell:** Allows generation of electrical energy in orbit.
6. **Deployment Switch:** Switches that are actuated, when the satellite is inserted in the launch device. When actuated, the power flow of solar cells and battery is interrupted.
7. **Remove Before Flight Pin:** While this pin is inserted into the satellite, power flow of battery and solar cells is interrupted.
8. **Voltage and Current Sensor:** Measures voltage and current readings. This information is collected by the housekeeping block. During the development it will be evaluated in detail which parameters are required.
9. **Battery Controller:** Controls charge- and discharge-rate of the battery pack. Monitors battery voltage level and temperature. Provides the “Battery OK” signal to the CubeSat Bus Interface.
10. **MPPT Controller:** Keeps the connected solar cell at its maximum point of power by utilizing a Maximum Point of Power Tracking mechanism (MPPT), in order to optimize energy generation. Provides a regulated voltage at its output.
11. **Deployment Timer:** Timer that is started once all DS are no longer actuated and the RBF has been removed. After expiration of the timer, an electrical signal is emitted.
12. **Housekeeping:** Collects data of the sensors on the EPS and provides this data via an interface.
13. **Umbilical Cord Interface (UCI):** Interface to the umbilical cord connector. This connector allows ground based debugging and battery charging after assembly of the CubeSat.
14. **CubeSat Bus Interface:** Interface to the CubeSat system bus.

System requirement 1 demands, that either the solar cells or the battery must be able to drive the power bus, if the respective other part is currently not able to provide power. This circumstance implies four states of operation. These states and the respective conditions of battery and solar cells are depicted in Table 3.2. The battery state *operable* and *not operable* refer to the ability of the battery to provide electrical power. The state *not operable* could be caused by a low charge level. In this case, this state is temporary, until the charge level is high enough again. Another reason for the *not operable* state is an internal short of the battery. This fault implies, that the battery is stuck in the *not operable* state, and can not recover.

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		Battery	
		Operable	Not operable
Solar cells	Generating	High power	Solar power only
	Not generating	Battery power only	No power

Table 3.2.: Combination of two possible states of battery and solar cells result in four possible states of operation.

Figure 3.5.: The power flow in the EPS during the respective states of operation.

3. System Architecture

The definition of the transition between these operation states is not within the scope of this document. It shall be specified latest in the upcoming EPS-PDR. The transition specification shall be verified by a “dataflow” game, where participants assume the role of a CubeSat subsystem. The operation of the CubeSat is then simulated by the participants (see Chapter 3 for details).

High power In this state, the solar cells generate power. The battery is operable and is being discharged or charged, depending on the current power demand of the subsystems and solar cell output. The power bus is driven by both, solar cells and battery. See Figure 3.5a for reference.

Solar power only Only the solar cells provide power. This may be caused by a low battery charge level, or a permanent battery fault. The power bus is only driven by the solar cells and the battery charger is bypassed over a diode. This means that the provided voltage on the bus may be volatile as the light incidence on the solar cells varies strongly over the orbit. The “Battery OK” signal issues this state to other systems, so they may act accordingly. See Figure 3.5b for reference.

Battery power only The solar cells do not provide any energy. This may be the case, if the CubeSat traverses the shade of the earth, or the solar cell contacts corrode. The power bus is driven by the battery charger, and in extension by the battery. This continues as long as there is charge left, or the solar cells provide power again. See Figure 3.5c for reference.

No power Solar cells and battery do not provide any power. In this state the power bus is not driven. The EPS does not provide any energy. This results in no operation of the CubeSat. See Figure 3.5d for reference.

Figure 3.6.: The block diagram of the EPS.

3.4.3. Interfaces

The EPS has an interface to the CubeSat system bus, where it provides a single power bus, a “Battery OK” signal and the housekeeping data. The EPS does not guarantee a fixed voltage level on the power bus. Other subsystems therefore have to implement additional voltage regulators to power its individual components. Furthermore, the EPS connects to the UCI. Here, the external charging port is connected. A listing of EPS in- and outputs (from an EPS point of view) can be seen in table 3.3 and table 3.4.

EPS System Bus Interface pins		
Name	Direction	Description
Power Bus	Out	Provides power to other systems
Housekeeping data	In/Out	Interface for a serial communication protocol that allows polling of housekeeping data
Battery OK	Out	Signal, that indicates, whether the battery is currently able to provide power.

Table 3.3.: Pins which connect the EPS to the system bus.

EPS Umbilical Cord pins		
Name	Direction	Description
Cell X +	In	Positive terminal of battery cell X
Cell X –	In	Negative terminal of battery cell X

Table 3.4.: Pins which connect the EPS to the umbilical cord interface (UCI).

3.5. COBC – Communication Module and On-board Computer

The COBC of the CubeSat STS1 combines two classical subsystems which are key components in every satellite mission: the Communication module (COM) and the On-Board Computer (OBC). The COM is responsible for any received and transmitted data and the OBC mainly schedules any activities on the CubeSat. Additionally, the OBC acts as the master module of the CubeSat platform by managing memory access and operating the EDU. This also concludes that the COBC is always the first subsystem that is powered up if energy becomes available. Other CubeSat components (except the EPS) are then enabled sequentially by the COBC, this includes the power up of the EDU module. Figure 3.7 shows the main components of the COBC system.

Figure 3.7.: Block diagram of the COBC with its main components. Furthermore, communication links, external interfaces, and the structure of the external memory are shown.

The Microcontroller Unit (MCU) is the COBC’s core and handles the entire dataflow on board the CubeSat. This means analyzing incoming and preparing outgoing data from and to the RF module (presumably RFM23B [18]), managing all data access – read, write and erase – to the external memories – based on (proposed) FRAM and Flash – and handling data exchange with the EDU module. Details regarding the external memory on the COBC are given in Section 3.5.4. Note that the MCU also schedules the operation of the EDU module. Another important feature is that the antenna deployment mechanism is triggered by the MCU as well.

The proposed concept combines the approach of an individual COM and OBC subsystem. To determine if separate systems are necessary, the dataflow, which is described in section 3.3, was thoroughly discussed. The main argument is that the capabilities of this CubeSat mission do not require separate COM and OBC subsystems, as these functionalities can be combined on a single subsystem: the COBC. The COBC section is divided into four subsections: Section 3.5.2 describes the functionality of the RF module. Further, Section 3.5.3 gives an insight on the MCU itself, whereas the associated external

memories are discussed in Section 3.5.4. Finally, Section 3.5.5 describes the concept of the antenna deployment mechanism.

3.5.1. Latch-up protection module

Latch-up is a condition when a low impedance path is created in a transistor, that is caused by a high energy particle or ionic radiation. The issue here is that once created, such a path remains active and can cause damage due to the high current level. There are specialized ICs developed to be immune to this problem, but they are out of reach for a regular CubeSat mission.

Thus, to protect the ICs from possible damage, the latch-up module is used: its functionality is to monitor the current consumption of the circuit that needs to be protected. An abrupt increase in current consumption is used as an indicator of a latch-up event taking place. When it happens, the latch-up module is responsible for cutting the power off as quickly as possible and keeping it off for the period of time necessary for the transient processes to finish. After that, the power is turned on, and the normal operation of the circuit in question is resumed.

3.5.2. RF Module

The RF module is the active part of the RF front end, which receives and transmits a binary stream from and to the GS via an RF link and forwards these data to the MCU for further processing. The RF stream is modulated onto an amateur radio frequency band (70 cm) carrier. Note that the RF link works in half-duplex operation to reduce complexity in hardware and management (software implementation). To be more explicit, this prevents any switching of antennas/transceivers and means that the CubeSat cannot receive and transmit data at the same time. A custom cross-dipole (made of metal ruler tape) is connected into a circular polarization using a delay line and power splitter/combiner.

As briefly introduced in Section 3.3, the whole RF link communication shall be amateur radio compliant. This means that the modulation scheme and filtering needs to be implemented according to amateur radio standards. Furthermore, it shall be possible to turn off the RF module by a command from the GS. This prevents the CubeSat from performing any further RF communication in the case that the used communication frequency is legally not usable anymore.

Because of thermal concerns with pre-built RF modules (often no way to properly keep them cool without ambient air), the decision was made to build the RF transceiver using discrete components. All critical integrated circuits used in the RF chain have already been used on other missions, like Lucky-7 and UVSQ-SAT [19] [20].

3.5.3. MCU – Microcontroller Unit

The MCU is the brain of the CubeSat. It handles all telemetry and housekeeping tasks required to keep the satellite operational. The functionality can be divided into the following main categories:

- System startup/initialization
- Communication
- System health data collection
- Scheduling of the operation time of the EDU

System startup/initialization

The first task of the MCU after deployment and power recovery is to initialize the internal peripherals and all external components which are connected to the MCU. If not explicitly deactivated, the antenna deployment mechanism is triggered (details can be found in Section 3.5.5). After a successfully verified antenna deployment², a command can be transmitted to the CubeSat to disable the antenna deployment mechanism. This ensures reduced power consumption during the regular boot operation of the CubeSat infrastructure. The deactivation of the antenna deployment mechanism is stored as a magic value in the COBC's external memory, including a checksum to prevent accidental deactivation due to random bit flips caused by radiation. Note that, any other execution of tasks (except the transmission of beacons) is triggered or managed from the GS, respectively. Dedicated assignment of data to FRAM or Flash can be seen in the COBC SW CDD [7].

Communication

The MCU also serves as the central communication hub of the CubeSat. It receives data from the RF and EDU modules and polls various sensor data – from sensors on the EPS and COBC – for the generation of the beacon data. The telemetry beacon is generated from said data in regular intervals (at least once a minute) and is sent to the RF module for transmission. It needs to be considered that the RF module merely receives packages and does not perform any integrity check. Therefore, the RF module just forwards the data to the COBC, where uplink data is first checked for data integrity and authenticity (Forward Error Correction (FEC) and signature) by the MCU. There are three possible types of uplink data: commands to be processed by the COBC, files (e.g. Python scripts or supporting data) meant for the EDU subsystem (including EDU execution queue files) and firmware updates for the COBC's MCU.

Commands are processed directly on the MCU as soon as resources for processing are available and downlink data is scheduled as soon as a command is successfully received. The scheduled downlink data is either a simple ACK or a response which in turn can require an ACK from the ground station to signal successful reception depending on the exact type of command and data.

Files for the EDU subsystem are stored on the external memory on the COBC. Note that the MCU is capable to transfer these files to the EDU for the execution on the Raspberry Pi. This also concludes that the MCU acts as master and the EDU as slave. This is of major importance to avoid any conflicts of interest between these two processing units.

Firmware updates ensure that the MCU on the COBC itself can be updated. Therefore, the firmware version on the MCU and the latest firmware version on the external memory are compared. It needs to be ensured that a reliable concept is developed to conduct these tasks. A promising procedure, which inspires us, is the implementation, which is done on the Mars Rover Curiosity [21]. If the firmware version on the MCU is not equal to the firmware version on the external memory and an according command is received, the firmware version on the external memory gets flashed onto the MCU by resetting the MCU itself. Afterwards, the MCU reboots with the new firmware. The Mars Rover Curiosity has an additional firmware image of the old firmware version as a fallback. Details are described in chapter 3 in the COBC SW CDD [22].

In the other direction, things work similarly as the COBC can pull data into the external memory from the Raspberry Pi memory. These data can then be transmitted to the GS via a command sent from the GS to the CubeSat. As the CubeSat does not send any data (except for beacons) without an explicit request from the GS, situations where no uplink is possible due to a saturated downlink

²Will be manually verified from the GS using metrics like signal strength.

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can be avoided. Downlink packets are queued in a priority-based queue as to not block beacons and commands with less important file transfers. For further protocol information see [23].

System health data collection

The third task of the MCU is to collect and store sensor data related to overall system health. This primarily consists of data generated by the EPS (e.g. bus current and voltage, solar cell status, battery voltage, charge/discharge current, battery state, temperatures, etc.) but also locally generated statistics like uplink packet FEC and re-transmission counts as well as signal strength, to name a few examples. Depending on the historical importance of data, it is either stored in (volatile) SRAM or (nonvolatile) FRAM. Apart from the regular telemetry packets, it is possible to request current and historical data directly. Long term data can be down sampled automatically after a certain amount of time to not lose old but not yet retrieved data in case the GS is unable to reach the satellite for extended time periods.

Scheduling EDU programs by queuing

As described in Section 3.3, the external memory contains an execution queue, which determines the order of operation of individual student software experiments on the EDU module. This allows us to keep an overview of the planned and already executed Python scripts. Furthermore, an organized handling of scripts and data is ensured. In the case of a power outage, the Python script will be executed at a later time as the queue remains in the external memory until the COBC obtains data from the EDU module. A more detailed definition will be done as soon as the development of the COBC progresses further. Additionally, this ensures that the MCU does not get corrupted by any rescheduling. Note that this also increases the level of reliability by reducing the complexity of the scheduling in comparison to a time-based mechanism.

3.5.4. External Memory

As shown in Figure 3.7, the external memory is divided into six main blocks: The FW MEM1 and FW MEM2 contain firmware updates for the COBC itself. Two separate memory blocks are necessary to implement the proposed concept which contains new firmware updates as well as an initial firmware version as a fallback. The EDU-relevant memory cells are EDU QUEUE and EDU MEM. EDU MEM contains the uploaded EDU programs and (processed) data which was generated by the execution of EDU programs, whereas EDU QUEUE contains the queuing procedures for student software experiments stored in EDU MEM. Finally, TELEMETRY HISTORY stores the telemetry and housekeeping data which is necessary for the beacon generation. All mentioned memory blocks are realized as FRAM or Flash. Details regarding its implementation will be done as the development of the COBC progresses further.

3.5.5. Antenna Deployment Mechanism

At the very beginning of the mission, the antennas are wrapped around the CubeSat and held in place by a plastic string. This string must be severed in order for the antennas to deploy, making the CubeSat ready for RF communication. The antenna deployment mechanism accomplishes this by running a current through a resistor which heats up by resistive heating and melts the string. Supplying power from the EPS to the resistor is done by a MOSFET which was already used in previous CubeSat missions, e.g. Pegasus [24].

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The antenna deployment is triggered approximately 5 minutes after the cobc is powered on. This allows to load more energy into the akkus than the antenna deployment requires, leading to never falling into a reset loop. The detailed management – activation at startup and deactivation by a telecommand – is explained in more detail in [7].

The following list gives a brief overview of some relevant features of the antenna deployment mechanism:

- According to first tests – where PLA zipties were melted – approximately 8.5Ws–25Ws are required.
- MOSFET: triggered by COBC
- The Antennas will also be tested in the undeployed position. Electrically isolating them from the frame may help reduce losses in this case.

3.6. EDU – Education Module

The education module (EDU) is the platform on which students can run their software experiments. It consists of a Raspberry Pi which has access to various sensors, including two cameras. The generated (and processed) data will be transferred to the COBC and stored on its external memory where it can be downloaded via a command. After a successful download, the data will be processed and handed over to the student teams to analyze it. The CubeSat is designed such that the EDU module is an independent payload, i.e. the CubeSat is fully operational without the EDU module or in the case of a complete failure of the module.

The EDU section is divided into three subsections: Section 3.6.1 gives an outline how the educational aspect of the mission fits into the global and national educational landscape. In Section 3.6.2 the different components of the EDU module and the data flow between them is discussed. Finally, Section 3.6.3 gives insights into thoughts about a supporting Attitude Determination and Control System (ADCS) and any redundancy concepts of the EDU module.

3.6.1. Educational Importance

Due to the increasing popularity of Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) components in space-related missions, the number of missions with an educational³ goal is steadily increasing. For example, in ESA's Astro Pi Challenge [25], students are able to run their code on a Raspberry Pi computer on-board the ISS. Furthermore, several educational CubeSat missions are currently in development or already in orbit, such as SelfieSat [26] or ArduSat [27].

Even though there are already established space-related educational missions, a hands-on approach seems out of reach for most people and thus we want to further lower the entry barrier for students in Austria and offer an approachable space education mission which will hopefully inspire the next generation of space and science enthusiasts. In comparison to the above-mentioned missions, STS1 will offer students an opportunity to develop their own software in close guidance with the TU Wien Space Team and run their code on an independent spacecraft in orbit around Earth. Furthermore, their code will be able to gather data during a prolonged period of time which allows more sophisticated software experiments as in comparison to ESA's Astro Pi Challenge where the runtime is limited to 3 hours. During the software development phase, students will be able to test their code on development kits which will further enhance their coding experience and give them the possibility of debugging their code. The supporting members of the TU Wien Space Team will be approachable during the whole development phase and can give valuable support to the students in their native language.

The EDU module of STS1 uses the popular Raspberry Pi platform [28]. This will further lower the entry barrier, both for teachers and students, as lots of resources about the platform are freely available on the Internet and some participants will already be familiar with the platform. In addition, we will try to keep the coding experience as accessible as possible by hosting workshops and providing libraries for the most common operations on the EDU module, i.e. for sensor readouts and standard commands for data processing. Furthermore, the Raspberry Pi platform will allow students to code their own software experiments in Python, which is nowadays one of the most popular [29] programming languages, especially for trending fields such as data science or machine learning. Thus, any familiarity with Python will greatly benefit the students in their later academic or professional careers.

Sensors under current consideration are: temperature sensors, magnetic field sensors, acceleration sensors, gyroscopes, GNSS receiver, cameras, strain gauges, brightness sensors, and a radiation sensor. Possible student experiments with these sensors are for example mapping the radiation environment of low Earth orbit (LEO) or determining how fast the CubeSat is spinning. Students who participate

³In the following, every mission with a goal to spark interest in science and space is considered an 'educational' mission.

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in STS1's educational mission will gain hands-on experience in writing actual space software, which will advance their problem-solving and teamwork skills. The whole mission will be held in form of a competition, where we expect to gain the support of Austrian space companies and space celebrities for honouring the winning teams. However, we will ensure that all participating student teams, not only the winning teams, will reach their software development goals.

As our educational mission seems in line with already well-established educational organizations in Austria, such as the Österreichische Forschungsförderungsgesellschaft FFG (Austrian Research Promotion Agency) [2] or the European Space Education Resource Office (ESERO) [1], we will get in contact with these and try to establish suitable cooperations, similar to how the TU Wien Space Team is already supporting ESERO's CanSat Challenge [30]. In the past year, this has not led to any cooperations, however we still try to establish cooperations.

3.6.2. Architecture

Figure 3.8 shows the main components of the EDU module.

Figure 3.8.: Block diagram of the EDU module with its main components. The black arrows mark data communication links.

A Raspberry Pi Compute Module 3 will be used as a processing unit in the development phase due to its excellent compromise between performance, power consumption, and heat generation. Moreover, the Raspberry Pi Compute Module 3 allows the connection of two Raspberry Pi camera modules V2 [31], which was already successfully used to capture images of Earth from space on-board SSTL's DoT-1 satellite [32], via two distinct Camera Serial Interfaces (CSI). The Raspberry Pi will be equipped

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with an eMMC Flash memory where the operating system and the file system for storage of EDU programs and EDU data will be located. The EPS will provide power for the EDU module. The necessary voltage levels will be generated on the EDU module. The connection to various sensors and the voltage generation will be enabled by a custom-made breakout board which will host the Raspberry Pi Compute Module in the CubeSat PCB stack.

We are confident that the chosen Raspberry Pi platform will be able to successfully operate in LEO for two reasons. First, different Raspberry Pi models were already successfully operated in space [33, 34]. Second, several radiation tests [35, 36, 37] suggest that different Raspberry Pi models can operate in radiation environments similar to LEO. If problems regarding the heat generation of the Raspberry Pi Compute Module 3 occur in the development phase, a change to use a Compute Module 1 will be considered. This change should be easily implementable as the Compute Module 1 and 3 have the same form factor and connections (same pin-out).

The COBC is able to turn on/off the entire EDU module and schedule the execution of EDU programs. The uploaded EDU programs will be transferred to the file system of the Raspberry Pi where they await the execution command from the COBC. If the COBC starts the execution of an EDU program, the Raspberry Pi can gather data from the connected sensors and cameras. This data can be processed on the Raspberry Pi's CPU and GPU. The (processed) data is temporarily stored on the Raspberry Pi's file system. For permanent storage, the EDU program code has to include certain save commands that will save the (processed) data on the COBC's external memory⁴. With this method, the EDU data downlink is independent of the operation status of the EDU module, i.e. the data can also be downlinked when the EDU module is completely turned off. For a more detailed discussion of the EDU data flow, see Section 3.3.5.

3.6.3. Supporting Systems and Redundancy

In the previous CubeSat project of the TU Wien Space Team, DISCO One [38], the use of an Attitude Determination and Control System (ADCS) was planned to ensure a proper orientation of the CubeSat for a stable optical communication link. The ADCS of DISCO One consisted of several magnetometers and gyroscopes to sense the orientation of the satellite and a magnetic torquer board to be able to slow down the spinning of the spacecraft after launch.

STS1 will not use an ADCS. This decision leads to less power consumption, complexity, and a shortened development and testing phase. The only component on board STS1 that would greatly benefit from an ADCS is the camera module. However, the operational CubeSat DAVE [39] was able to capture an image of Earth with a cell phone camera without the use of an ADCS. Thus, we strive to replicate this success with rigorous testing of STS1's camera performance.

The use of two cameras, mounted on opposing sides of the CubeSat, with a large field of view will give us the opportunity to image Earth in all possible orientations of the CubeSat. If STS1 is spinning after deployment, we will adjust the settings (brightness, exposure time,...) of the camera to be able to acquire a sharp image. This procedure will be extensively tested in the upcoming development phase. If the initial spinning of the CubeSat exceeds the capabilities of our camera module to acquire a sharp image, we will focus on the operation of the other systems and sensors until the satellite has slowed down its rotation by atmospheric drag. Even if the rotation speed of STS1 is too fast for a sharp image acquisition over the entire lifetime, no primary mission objective is compromised by the decision of not using an ADCS. Besides the camera, all other systems of STS1 (including the sensors of the EDU module) will be able to operate nominally without an ADCS.

⁴The COBC is always the master system regarding COBC and EDU communication. This includes the above-mentioned saving operation.

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Traditional space missions often use redundant components to lower the risk of failure of certain components or whole (sub)systems. However, the incorporation of redundancy always comes with an increased complexity of the entire system and thus needs significant development and testing time in order to benefit from the incorporated redundancy. Thus, we decided not to integrate the EDU module in a redundant manner for two main reasons. First, STS1 is the first self-developed CubeSat mission of the TU Wien Space Team, which means that already a significant amount of development time is needed to establish a reliably working CubeSat platform – even without incorporating redundant systems. Second, in the former preliminary concept of STS1, the redundant systems were heavily criticized by external reviewers. Therefore, our goal is to develop a working CubeSat hardware early on and start with systematic (automatic) testing of the individual CubeSat subsystems and the whole CubeSat stack as early as possible.

Even though major systems will not be implemented in a redundant manner, we have concerns that the eMMC memory of the Raspberry Pi platform is vulnerable to the radiation environment in LEO. Thus, we are investigating the usage of a system that would allow the Raspberry Pi to boot from multiple eMMCs. The firmware that runs on the Raspberry Pi will not be able to receive a firmware update as the needed functionality is limited. Additionally, extensive testing of the used EDU platform will be performed on ground before launch. Therefore, the only critical error handling scheme of the EDU module is the restart via a command of the COBC and potentially a switchover to a redundant eMMC memory.

3.7. Student Cooperation

One of the primary objectives of STS1 is to inspire students and offer them the possibility to be part of a space project. To achieve this, cooperations between STS1 and several schools are established before launch. The step-by-step plan for how the pupils and students participate in the project is listed below:

1. STS1 gets into contact with a teacher of a school that wants to participate.
2. An initial meeting is set up where the teacher is informed of the plan.
3. The teacher receives two EDU Development Kits to experiment and test as well as instructions on how to work with the EDU Development Kits.
4. The teacher tests everything and talks with his or her school as well as the possible class about the project.
5. Students develop projects in the school or with support from the school. If questions arise STS1 is asked and answers within several days.
6. Once the CubeSat is in orbit the next phase can begin.
7. Once a student program is finished it is sent to STS1 to verify the functionality and safety. If all the tests of the program succeed on the ground testing station, a timeslot when the program should be executed is organized in cooperation between the students and STS1.
8. STS1 sends the program to the CubeSat and instructs it to be executed at the decided on time.
9. The CubeSat autonomously executes the program and saves the result file.
10. STS1 instructs the CubeSat to send the result file back to Earth.
11. STS1 sends the result file and a certificate of participation to the students who created the program.

The verification of the student programs is done on an FM version of the CubeSat which is partly assembled, electronic systems are connected, and located at the main building of the TU Wien Space Team. This setup can be placed in a testing station developed by the HTL Rankweil in Vorarlberg and located at the main building of the TU Wien Space Team. During the testing, the program is executed and the power level of the system is tracked.

Currently we are in contact with three school that support us with pupil projects, expertise and contacts. Additionally we are in contact with twelve school that participate in the project to develop code to be run in space. Those schools are in different stages of the project, one is in stage 2, two are in stage 4, eight are in stage 5.

4. Discussion

During the PDR several minor points were addressed by the reviewers:

1. **Definition of operable unclear:** The term "operable" in requirement 8 is unclear.
2. **Ground station database:** We shall use a database that other GS use as well, so we can switch gs if needed.
3. **RF packaging:** The communication packaging is not described in detail. A lost package shall not stop us from being able to communicate with the satellite.
4. **Electric motor:** External wiring of the EPS shall not produce an electric motor. Twisted pairs on the SC connections. Flatband should be OK.
5. **Batteries in low temperatures:** What happens to our batteries if they are -40° can we draw power for Antenna Deployment?
6. **Naming:** Master / Slave should not be used (in 6), maybe we find a better terminology.
7. **Wrong figures:** In 3.1 the link between UCI and COBC is wrong. The PC should be in the GS.

A. Appendix

A.1. Power Budget

STS1 Power Budget Solar Array Sizing

Key:
User Input
Calculation result
Constant

Silicon Solar Array	
Mission Life Time	0.5 years
Power Input	1358 W/m ²
Efficiency	25 %
Power Out (Po)	339.50 W/m ²
Inherent Degradation (Id)	0.77
Array Degradation (3.75%/yr)	0.98

Panel Dimensions	
Width	0.06 m
Length	0.06 m
Area	0.0036 m ²

Power Generated / panel				
Incidence Angle	0	30	45	60
Power Generated (BOL)	0.94	0.82	0.67	0.47 W
Power Generated (EOL)	0.92	0.80	0.65	0.46 W

Power Generated	
	Power
Corner points to sun	1.38 W
Face points to sun	0.92 W
Edge points to sun	1.31 W
Mean	1.20 W

A. Appendix

ST51 Power Budget
Power Budget

Percent of time in Sun
Initial Orbit Period
Initial Orbit Period

Key:
User Input
Calculation result
Constant

Quick Summary - Power Usage	
Day Power	1.1 W
Night Power	1.0 W
Orbit Average	0.82 W

60.52 % percent
5507.4 sec
1.53 hours

	Voltage	Component Power (W)	Day/Night/ Both	Day Power (W)	Day Duty Cycle	Day Avg Power (W)	Night Power (W)	Night Duty Cycle	Night Avg Power (W)	Orbit Avg Power(W)	Peak Power(W)
EDU		3.42		3.42		0.70		2.62		0.70	3.42
Camera	3.3	0.80	Day	0.80	0.01	0.01		0.00		0.00	
Raspberry Pi active	3.3	2.40	Both	2.40	0.20	0.48		2.40		0.48	
Sensors (Temp, gyro, accel,...)	3.3	0.01	Both	0.01	0.20	0.00		0.01		0.00	
GPS	3.3	0.18	Both	0.18	1.00	0.18		0.18		0.18	
Dosimeter	3.3	0.03	Both	0.03	1.00	0.03		0.03		0.03	
OBC		0.12		0.12		0.06		0.12		0.06	0.12
Processor	5	0.05	Both	0.05	1.00	0.05		0.05		0.05	
Sensors	3.3	0.01	Both	0.01	0.20	0.00		0.01		0.00	
Memory (2x FRAM, 1x Flash)	3.3	0.06	Both	0.06	0.20	0.01		0.06		0.01	
COM		2.88		2.88		0.04		2.88		0.05	2.88
S/C Receiver (Active)	2.5	0.13	Both	0.13	0.02	0.00		0.13		0.00	
S/C Transmitter (Active)	2.5	2.75	Both	2.75	0.02	0.04		2.75		0.05	
EPS		0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	0.00
		0.00	Day	0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00		0.00	
Total Avg Power						0.81				0.83	6.42
Power Design Margin		5 %				0.04				0.04	0.32
Subtotal Power						0.85				0.86	6.74
Charging and Conversion Losses						0.25				0.22	2.48
Battery Charging (Efficiency 90%)						0.08				0.05	0.94
Power Conversion (80%)		0.75				0.17				0.17	1.54
Power Required (W)						1.09				1.04	8.89
Power Available (W)						1.20				0.73	
Power Balance (W)						0.11				-1.04	

STS1 Power Budget

Battery Sizing

Battery parameters		
Bus Voltage	3,2	V
Orbit Period	1,53	h
Mission Life	4383	h
Charge/Discharge Cycles	2865	cycles
Eclipse Time	0,60	h
Power Consumption at night	1,041	W
Depth of Discharge Max	30 %	percent
Discharge Efficiency	90 %	percent
Consumend energy per eclipse	0,70	Wh
Total Capacity	2,33	Wh

Battery Charging		
Charge Energy	0,70	Wh
Orbit Day Length	0,93	h
Charge Power	0,75	W

Cell Comparison			
	SAFT VHAA 1200	SAFT SL18650	
Cell Voltage	1,2	3,6	V
Cell Capacity	1,3	1,66	Ah
Cell Energy	1,56	5,976	Wh
Min # Cells	2	1	cells
Battery Pack Properties (Required)			
# Battery Packs Required	1	1	Battery Packs
# Cells Per Battery Pack	3	1	cells
Nominal Voltage/Pack	3,6	3,6	V
Total Battery Pack Capacity	4,68	6	Wh
DOD Typical	15 %	12 %	percent

A.2. Initial Project plan from 2020

Figure A.1.: Gantt chart for the high-altitude flight (HAF) of STS1. In retrospect, there was a delay of about 20%.

A.3. Financial budget

2021			
Kostenstellen	Kosten	Einkünfte	Anmerkungen
Prototypen	€ 4 557.84	€ 0.00	
TU Wien Space Team	€ 0.00	€ 4 557.84	Sponsoren und Förderungen
Summe 2021	€ 4 557.84	€ 4 557.84	

2022			
Kostenstellen	Kosten	Einkünfte	Anmerkungen
High Altitude Flight	€ 925.00	€ 0.00	
Bodenstation Elektronik	€ 20.29	€ 0.00	
Bodenstation Mechanik	€ 236.61	€ 0.00	
CubeSat Elektronik	€ 8 241.65	€ 0.00	
CubeSat Mechanik	€ 455.60	€ 0.00	
TU Wien Space Team	€ 0.00	€ 9 879.15	Sponsoren und Förderungen
Summe 2022	€ 9 879.15	€ 9 879.15	

2023			
Kostenstellen	Kosten	Einkünfte	Anmerkungen
Schulmanagement	€ 405.50	€ 0.00	
Bodenstation	€ 519.78	€ 0.00	
Elektronik	€ 16 253.46	€ 0.00	
Mechanik	€ 1 620.11	€ 1 000.00	Schnaidt Sponsoring
Externe Kosten	€ 2 553.03	€ 0.00	Testequipment, Reisekosten, Konferenzkosten
TU Wien Space Team	€ 0.00	€ 20 351.88	Sponsoren und Förderungen
Summe 2023	€ 21 351.88	€ 21 351.88	

Figure A.2.: Financial budget for STS1 for 2021,2022, and 2023.

A. Appendix

2021			
Kostenstellen	Kosten	Einkünfte	Anmerkungen
Prototypen	€ 4 557.84	€ 0.00	
TU Wien Space Team	€ 0.00	€ 4 557.84	Sponsoren und Förderungen
Summe 2021	€ 4 557.84	€ 4 557.84	

2022			
Kostenstellen	Kosten	Einkünfte	Anmerkungen
High Altitude Flight	€ 925.00	€ 0.00	
Bodenstation Elektronik	€ 20.29	€ 0.00	
Bodenstation Mechanik	€ 236.61	€ 0.00	
CubeSat Elektronik	€ 8 241.65	€ 0.00	
CubeSat Mechanik	€ 455.60	€ 0.00	
TU Wien Space Team	€ 0.00	€ 9 879.15	Sponsoren und Förderungen
Summe 2022	€ 9 879.15	€ 9 879.15	

2023			
Kostenstellen	Kosten	Einkünfte	Anmerkungen
Schulmanagement	€ 405.50	€ 0.00	
Bodenstation	€ 519.78	€ 0.00	
Elektronik	€ 16 253.46	€ 0.00	
Mechanik	€ 1 620.11	€ 1 000.00	Schnaidt Sponsoring
Externe Kosten	€ 2 553.03	€ 0.00	Testequipment, Reisekosten, Konferenzkosten
TU Wien Space Team	€ 0.00	€ 20 351.88	Sponsoren und Förderungen
Summe 2023	€ 21 351.88	€ 21 351.88	

Figure A.3.: Financial budget for STS1 for 2024.

A.4. Orbit lifetime estimation

Figure A.4.: Estimated lifetime of STS1 in orbit before reentry.
Left: start 01.01.2024. Right: start 31.12.2024

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